

**PEER STUDY AND INDIVIDUALIZED LEARNING IN ACADEMIC
PERFORMANCE OF THE SELECTED JUNIOR HIGH
SCHOOL LEARNERS**

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Peer Study and Individualized Learning in Academic Performance of the Selected Junior High School Learners

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Abstract

This study determined the relationship between the learner's level of preference in terms of peer study and individualized learning and the learners' academic performance. Further, this study aimed to propose intervention programs to enhance the learners' educational performance through peer study and/or individualized learning. This study utilized a quantitative correlational and comparative research design to determine the relationship between the learner's level of preference in peer study and individualized education and the learners' academic performance. This study was conducted at Talisay High School during the school year 2022-2023 with two hundred thirty-two (232) selected Junior High School learners as respondents. Random sampling was employed to specify the total number of respondents, and the sample size was determined using the Yamane Formula. Mean, standard deviation and percentage were used to determine the level of preference to peer study and individualized learning. Moreover, Paired T test was used to measure the significant differences between the peer study and the individualized learning and Pearson R correlational coefficient was used to measure the linear association between variables. In addition, the researchers utilized an adapted modified questionnaire from Uzezi and Deya (2017) which underwent validation and reliability tests by experts. Based on the findings, there was a significant difference between the learners' preference level regarding peer study and individualized learning. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected. This means that peer study and individualized learning are distinct and utilized by the learners. Moreover, peer study is not significantly associated with learners' academic performance; thus, the null hypothesis failed to be rejected. On the other hand, there was a significant relationship between the learners' preference for individualized learning and the academic performance of the learners. Thus, learners who preferred individualized learning excelled more in classes, increasing their academic performance. Since peer study is not significantly associated with the academic performance, the proposed intervention program is focused on improving peer study as a strategy to enhance the academic performance of the learners because peer study is still significantly preferred by the learners, like individualized learning. It is recommended that educators, parents, and school administrators are encouraged to prioritize and promote individualized learning approaches in the classroom and apply the proposed intervention program for both peer study and individualized learning.

Keywords: *academic performance, peer study, individualized learning, cognitive, affective, psychomotor*

Introduction

Education is overwhelmingly the building block for an individual's success in society. Regardless, this success is not absolute, as a person's education greatly depends on performance. Thus, teachers must not only teach in their classrooms but also develop a means of evaluating their learners' learning throughout each instructional unit. Specifically, it employs an approach called peer study and individualized learning in the learners' academic performance. Through these strategies, educators can identify learners' strengths and weaknesses while encouraging learners' strengths and discouraging or removing any weaknesses if they persist through instruction. A broad-based education needs to evolve into something that is both skill, attitude, and knowledge base. That being said, society has come to expect a high literacy level from learners. In other words, there is a consensus among educators that gives them a purpose for why they are teaching: to prepare learners for employment and build future generations.

Education is essential for societal development and individual success. Since it affects us so frequently, we seldom stop to think about what it implies. Learning is the process of gaining new abilities, information, perspectives, and values (Malec, 2022). While people can accomplish learning on their own, it's usually made easier with the help of others or peers.

Peer study is a learning strategy that allows a person to study with a companion or friends. It is an educational approach where learners assist and educate one another. It is beneficial to the learners, especially in reaching learning outcomes (Williamson, 2018). Peer learning and learning by doing are two aspects of the same process, so putting learners at the forefront will increase cognitive skills and abilities, making them independent thinkers (Vallikat, 2021). Further, peer study develops communication skills that strengthen social skills and impart knowledge to the learners. Learners not only develop learning but also develop social skills. It can also help the learners to learn better by showing that learning can exist with each other. Therefore, learners can choose what they think would be most beneficial in achieving personal and academic goals.

On the other hand, some learners may choose to learn through self-paced learning, which is called individualized learning. It refers to educational opportunities where the learning pace is changed to match the needs of the learners. In other words, each learner experiences the same thing, but they all proceed at their unique paces (Cullata, 2022). Moreover, it is a common way for learners to study to gain

more knowledge; hence, a learner can strive for optimal achievement and develop self-management skills. It also allows the learners to learn in much greater depth and detail, which is needed in many fields of study and will enable individuals to explore personal interests.

Additionally, individualized learning refers to a learning approach that focuses on individual learners by targeting strengths and areas of weakness. This usually involves working independently, and the learners are expected to reach their personal goals without help from others. Peer study and/or individualized learning are being used in different schools to help learners develop academic performance (Williamson, 2018; Fink, 2020; Vallikat, 2021; Liu et al., 2022; Cox, 2022). These learning strategies can be effective if the learners are willing to learn. Learners feel more confident, motivated, and self-assured when using more strategies (Shi, 2017). Furthermore, because of their strong theoretical foundation in education, these learning strategies have been used to provide a more effective approach to education. With such strong claims and benefits, the researchers should conduct this study in a way relevant to peer and individualized studies.

This study focuses on determining the significant relationship between peer and individualized learning and the learners' academic performance. It also focuses on the implications of both learning strategies for the learners' overall performance.

Research Questions

The study aimed to determine the relationship between peer study, individualized learning, and learners' academic performance. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of preference of the selected Junior High School learners as regards the peer study in terms of:
 - 1.1. cognitive;
 - 1.2. affective; and
 - 1.3. psychomotor
2. What is the level of preference of the selected Junior High School learners as regards individualized learning in terms of:
 - 2.1. cognitive;
 - 2.2. affective; and
 - 2.3. psychomotor
3. What is the academic performance of the Selected Junior High School learners at Talisay High School?
4. Is there a significant difference in the level of preference for peer study and individualized learning regarding the academic performance of the selected Junior High School?
5. Is there a significant relationship between peer study and the academic performance of the selected Junior High School?
6. Is there a significant relationship between individualized learning and the academic performance of the selected Junior High School?
7. What intervention program can be proposed to enhance the learners' academic performance through peer study and/or individualized learning?

Literature Review

Learners perform better in school when they develop their learning skills, which can be enhanced through individualized or peer study. Peer study fosters values, relationships, and community ties, providing a collaborative and engaging learning experience that improves attitudes and academic performance (Mulder et al., 2013; Williamson, 2018; Fink, 2020; Vallikat, 2021). It involves learners helping and teaching each other, which enhances social skills and creates a sense of community (ViewSonic, 2021; Jotheeswaran, 2022).

Individualized learning tailors the learning pace to each student, allowing them to explore their strengths and weaknesses, control their learning process, and maintain interest and motivation (Centre, 2021; Liu et al., 2022; Cox, 2022; Piccola et al., 2022; Pourhassan et al., 2022). Both strategies, peer and individualized learning, positively impact academic performance by catering to individual needs and fostering collaborative environments.

Academic performance is influenced by the time and attention given to learning, and it is crucial for learners' cognitive, affective, and behavioral development. Improved academic performance positively impacts learners' knowledge, attitudes, self-esteem, and motivation (Ruben, 2016; Culatta, 2016; Narad et al., 2016; Yusuf et al., 2016; Busalim et al., 2019; Kumar et al., 2021; Tadese et al., 2022).

Methodology

Research Design

The study utilized quantitative correlational and comparative research designs, which helped the researchers determine the relationship between peer study and individualized learning and learners' academic performance and the difference between the learners' levels of preference for peer study and individualized learning.

Respondents

This study utilized a random sampling to select the (232) two-hundred thirty-two Junior High School learners as the study's respondents. The total number of sample size was determined using the Yamane Formula. Further, the study was conducted during the S.Y. 2022-2023 at Talisay High School, Division of Batangas, due to its accessibility to the researchers, which was suitable for achieving the study's objectives

Instruments

The researchers adapted and modified a questionnaire from Uzezi and Deya (2017). The questionnaire was divided into two sections, namely, peer study and individualized learning, and further divided into three sub-indicators: cognitive, affective, and psychomotor. Each sub-indicator had five indicators, resulting in 30 indicators for the entire research instrument. The instruments were validated by three expert validators and subjected to reliability and validity tests. The adviser received a draft of the questionnaire for comments and corrections of the validated questionnaire.

The first part of the questionnaire had a response format with the following rating scale: (5) 90% and above= Advanced; (4) 85-89%= Proficiency; (3) 80-84%= Approaching Proficiency; (2) 75-79%= Developing; (1) 74% and above= Beginning. This part was used to measure the academic performance of the respondents based on the respondents' semestral general weighted average (GWA). On the other hand, the second part of the questionnaire had the following rating scale: 4 = strongly agree; 3 = agree; 2 = disagree; 1 = disagree. The researchers used this to determine the respondents' level of preference for the indicators provided regarding the subject of the study.

Procedure

The researchers utilized an adapted modified questionnaire from Uzezi & Deya (2017). The adapted modified instruments underwent validation and reliability tests by experts. In collecting data, the researchers sent a consent and request letter to the principal, advisers, and parents of the respondents/learners, seeking permission to conduct the study. The researchers explained the purpose of the study and the ethical considerations that will be applied. The research instrument was then administered to all respondents, and they were asked to respond honestly and truthfully. Afterward, data analysis and interpretation were conducted immediately after the questionnaires were retrieved. The data gathered were also treated with the utmost confidentiality.

Data Analysis

The data that was gathered in this study was subjected to the following statistical treatment:

Statement of the problem 1; To answer the problem no. 1, the formula for calculating percentages was used to identify the academic performance of the respondents.

Statement of the problem 2 and 3; To answer problem no. 2 and 3 the formula mean was used in identifying the academic performance of the respondents in terms of peer study and individualized learning, the level of preference of the respondents as regards the peer study and individualized learning in terms of cognitive, affective, and psychomotor, and the level of effectiveness of peer study and individualized learning on academic performance of the respondents.

Statement of the problem; To answer problem no. 4, the Paired T-Test was used to measure the significant differences between the peer study and the individualized learning.

Statement of the problem 5 and 6; To answer problem no. 5 and 6, the Pearson R correlational coefficient was used to measure the linear association between the peer study and the academic performance, between individualized learning and the academic performance of the respondents. It was used to determine if there was no significant relationship using this formula.

Ethical Considerations

The researchers recognized that collecting the learners' grades gave rise to privacy and security issues for the respondents who were used in the study. The respondent's rights and privacy were observed and addressed. The researchers were also prudent in the use of the obtained data. They adhered to all applicable laws, rules, and regulations, particularly human subjects' research and informed consent procedures.

The questions and answers were anonymous, not to enforce social pressure or stigma on the respondents. The researchers ensured the privacy and confidentiality of the collected data. They only provided the information to authorized persons and created an institutional environment free from prejudice, bias, and political pressure. The researchers modified the questionnaire to suit different social locations and conditions. They did not allow the data on study findings to be used for any purpose.

Results and Discussion

1. Learners' Academic Performance

Table 1 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents. The data shows that learners' proficiency was highest,

with most of the respondents at a proficiency level of 85-89%. The researchers interpreted this as most of the respondents being proficient based on the DepEd Learner's Proficiency level.

Table 1. *Learners' Academic Performance*

<i>Learners' Proficiency Level</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Description</i>
74% and below	7	3.02%	Beginning
75 - 79%	26	11.21%	Developing
80 - 84%	45	19.4%	Approaching Proficiency
85 - 89%	126	54.31%	Proficient
90% and above	28	12.1%	Advanced
Total	232	100%	

90% and above = Advanced; 85-89% = Proficient; 80-84% = Approaching Proficiency; 75-79% = Developing; 74% and above = Beginning

2. Level of Preference of the Learners to the Peer Study

2.1 Cognitive

Table 2.1. *Level of Preference of the Learners to the Peer Study in Terms of Cognitive*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>VI</i>
As a student, I...		
1. can recall the lessons with the help of my peers.	3.19	Agree
2. can summarize and understand the lessons with the help of my peers.	3.20	Agree
3. can apply my learnings in each activity with the help of my peers.	3.15	Agree
4. can evaluate and collaborate on each topic into meaningful learning with the help of my peers.	3.17	Agree
5. can create projects/learning outputs together with my peers.	3.28	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean	3.20	Agree

Legend: 4.00-3.25-Strongly Agree, 3.24-2.50-Agree, 2.49-1.75-Disagree, 1.74-1.00-Strongly Disagree
M-Mean, VI-Verbal Interpretation

The results of Table 2.1 show that most of the respondents Agree that they can effectively learn with the help of their peers. These findings highlight the importance of peer group studies in improving students' academic performance and overall learning experience.

2.2 Affective

Table 2.2. *Level of Preference of the Learners to the Peer Study in Terms of Affective*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>VI</i>
As a student, I...		
1. feel motivated when I am in my peer group.	3.21	Agree
2. appreciate the value of each lesson when my peers help me.	3.25	Strongly Agree
3. am confident in my performance when I have peers to share.	3.23	Agree
4. am eager to learn when my peers support me.	3.24	Agree
5. seek help and support from my peers when facing academic challenges.	3.29	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean	3.24	Agree

Legend: 4.00-3.25-Strongly Agree, 3.24-2.50-Agree, 2.49-1.75-Disagree, 1.74-1.00-Strongly Disagree
M-Mean, VI-Verbal Interpretation

Based on the result of Table 2.2, it is seen that most of the respondents do agree that they can benefit from peer learning in terms of affective factors such as seeking help and support from their peers when facing academic challenges, appreciating the value of each lesson when their peers help them, being eager to learn when their peers support them, feeling confident in their performances when they have peers to share with, and feeling motivated when they are with their peer group (Liu & Chen, 2020).

2.3 Psychomotor

Table 2.3. *Level of Preference of the Learners to the Peer Study in Terms of Psychomotor*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>VI</i>
As a student, I...		
1. can follow the target learning competencies with the help of my peers.	3.09	Agree
2. can perform the target learning competencies with the help of my peers.	3.03	Agree
3. can demonstrate the target learning competencies with the help of my peers.	3.04	Agree
4. can adapt and modify my performance based on the target learning competencies with the help of my peers.	3.04	Agree
5. use and apply my learning in my daily life with the help of my peers.	3.13	Agree
Overall Mean	3.07	Agree

Legend: 4.00-3.25-Strongly Agree, 3.24-2.50-Agree, 2.49-1.75-Disagree, 1.74-1.00-Strongly Disagree
M-Mean, VI-Verbal Interpretation

Table 2.3 presents the indicators about the level of preference of the learners regarding the peer study in terms of psychomotor. It is seen that most of the respondents do agree that they can benefit from peer learning in terms of psychomotor factors such as using and

applying their learning in their daily life with the help of their peers, following the target learning competencies with the help of their peers, demonstrating the target learning competencies with the help of their peers, and adapting and modifying their performance based on the target learning competencies with the help of their peers.

3. Level of Preference of the Learners for the Individualized Learning

3.1 Cognitive

Table 3.1. *Level of Preference of the Learners for Individualized Learning in Terms of Cognitive*

Indicators	M	VI
As a student, I...		
1. can recall the lessons independently.	2.93	Agree
2. can summarize and understand the lessons independently.	2.89	Agree
3. can apply my learnings in each activity independently.	2.82	Agree
4. can evaluate and collaborate each topic into meaningful learnings independently.	2.85	Agree
5. can create projects/learn independently.	2.91	Agree
Overall Mean	2.88	Agree

Legend: 4.00-3.25-Strongly Agree, 3.24-2.50-Agree, 2.49-1.75-Disagree, 1.74-1.00-Strongly Disagree
M-Mean, VI-Verbal Interpretation

Table 3.1 presents the indicators about the level of preference of the learners for individualized learning in terms of cognitive. It is seen that most of the respondents agree that they possess certain mental skills that are important for individualized learning, such as recalling lessons independently, creating projects/learning independently, summarizing and understanding lessons independently, evaluating and collaborating each topic into meaningful learnings independently, and applying learnings in each activity independently.

3.2 Affective

Table 3.2. *Level of preference of the Learners to the Individualized Learning in Terms of Affective*

Indicators	M	VI
As a student, I...		
1. feel motivated when I am alone.	2.80	Agree
2. appreciate the value of each lesson independently.	2.89	Agree
3. confident in my performance when I work alone.	2.74	Agree
4. am eager to learn when I am alone.	2.76	Agree
5. cope with academic challenges independently.	2.84	Agree
Overall Mean	2.81	Agree

Legend: 4.00-3.25-Strongly Agree, 3.24-2.50-Agree, 2.49-1.75-Disagree, 1.74-1.00-Strongly Disagree
M-Mean, VI-Verbal Interpretation

Based on Table 3.2, most of the respondents agree that they possess certain affective skills that are important for individualized learning, such as appreciating the value of each lesson independently, coping with academic challenges independently, feeling motivated when alone, being eager to learn when alone, and feeling confident in their performances when working alone.

3.3 Psychomotor

Table 3.3. *Level of preference of the Learners to the Individualized Learning in Terms of Psychomotor*

Indicators	M	VI
As a student, I...		
can follow the target learning competencies independently.	2.91	Agree
can perform the target learning competencies independently.	2.88	Agree
can demonstrate the target learning competencies independently.	2.82	Agree
can independently adapt and modify my performance based on the target learning competencies.	2.76	Agree
use and apply my learning in my daily life independently.	2.88	Agree
Overall Mean	2.85	Agree

Legend: 4.00-3.25-Strongly Agree, 3.24-2.50-Agree, 2.49-1.75-Disagree, 1.74-1.00-Strongly Disagree
M-Mean, VI-Verbal Interpretation

Table 3.2 shows that most of the respondents agree that they possess certain psychomotor skills that are important for individualized learning, such as following and performing target learning competencies independently, using and applying their knowledge in daily life, demonstrating target learning competencies independently, and adapting and modifying their performance based on target learning competencies independently (Sportsman et al., 2011).

4. Significant Differences between the Level preferences as to Peer Study and Individualized Learning

Table 4. *Significant Differences between the Level preferences as to Peer Study and Individualized Learning*

Variables	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Decision	Interpretation
Peer Study	.32483	.74898	6.606	231	< 0.01	Reject H ₀	Significant
Individualized Learning							

p < 0.05-Significant, *p* > 0.05-Not Significant

Using a paired T-test, SPSS results are displayed in Table 4, comparing Peer Study and Individualized Learning, with a t value of .32483 and a Significant value of < 0.01; thus, the null hypothesis was rejected. This means there were significant differences between the Peer Study and Individualized Learning.

5. Significant Relationship Between Peer Study and Academic Performance

Table 5. Significant Relationship Between Peer Study and Academic Performance

Variables	r value	p-value	Decision (Ho)	Interpretation
Peer Study and Academic Performance	.080	.225	Failed to reject	Not Significant

p < 0.05-Significant, *p* > 0.05-Not Significant

Using correlation, SPSS results are displayed in Table 5 about the relationship between the Peer Study and the Academic Performance of the Learners. In terms of the Peer Study and the Academic Performance, the R-value of .080 or the P-value of .225; thus, the null hypothesis failed to be rejected. This means that there was no significant relationship between the Peer Study and the Academic Performance of the learners.

6. Significant Relationship between Individualized Learning and Academic Performance

Table 6. Significant Relationship between Individualized Learning and Academic Performance

Variables	r value	p-value	Decision (Ho)	Interpretation
Individualized Learning and Academic Performance	.209	.001	Reject Ho	Significant (Positive Correlation)

p < 0.05-Significant, *p* > 0.05-Not Significant

Table 6 displays SPSS results about the relationship between individualized learning and academic performance using correlation. In terms of Individualized Learning and Academic Performance, with the R-value of .209 or P-value of .001, the null hypothesis is rejected. This means that there was a significant relationship between Individualized Learning and the learners' Academic Performance.

7. Intervention program for Junior High School regarding the Relationship between Peer Study and Academic Performance

Improving Academic Performance: Interventions and Benefits of Peer Study in Junior High School

Key Areas	Goals/Objectives	Activities/Strategies	Person Involve	Time Frame	Resources Needed	Success Indicators
Peer Study/ Academic Performance	To promote positive peer influence and enhance academic performance among learners.	Peer mentorship program where academically successful students can mentor and tutor struggling students	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> School Administrators Teachers Students Parents Mentors/Tutors 	6 months after school year started- 1 year	Supervision Training Educational Materials	80% Positive feedback from students on the peer mentorship program and selection of academically focused peers
	To reduce negative peer pressure that may affect academic performance	Survey to identify students who are engaged in negative peer pressure and provide interventions such as counseling and support groups		6 months after school year started- 1 year	Survey tools	85% Positive feedback from teachers and staff on the effectiveness of the interventions
	To improve academic performance of students in the school	Sports teams/ extracurricular activity that promote positive peer interactions and team building		Ongoing throughout the school year	Sports equipment Facilities Administrative and Parental Support	90% Increase in student engagement in extracurricular activities
		Training to teachers and staff on how to identify and address negative peer influence		Within the First month of the School year	Teachers' support and participation	95% of teachers and staff can identify negative peer influence and have strategies in place to address it.

Based on the study's results, peer study is not significantly associated with the academic performance of the learners. Thus, the intervention program is focused on improving peer study as a strategy to enhance the academic performance of the learners. In addition, this is because peer study is significantly preferred by the learners, like individualized learning.

Conclusions

The study revealed notable differences between peer study and individualized learning. These two methods of learning have distinct effects on learners' academic performance, suggesting that educators should carefully consider which approach best aligns with the desired learning outcomes and adapt their teaching strategies accordingly.

The study found no significant correlation between peer study and academic performance. This indicates that peer study alone may not have a substantial impact on improving academic performance. Other factors, such as learner motivation, individual learning

differences, and the quality of instruction, may also play significant roles in determining academic achievement.

Conversely, a significant relationship was observed between individualized learning and academic performance. This highlights the positive impact of individualized learning on learners' academic outcomes. Educators and institutions should, therefore, consider incorporating individualized learning activities, which can effectively enhance learning outcomes and academic performance.

It is recommended that school administrators support these methods by providing professional development for faculty, enhancing their understanding of these approaches, and equipping them with the necessary skills and knowledge. Administrators should also allocate resources for relevant materials and technological tools. Faculty members should assess students' learning needs and preferences to tailor instructional strategies, balancing individualized learning and peer study to offer a comprehensive learning experience. Parents should be informed about individualized learning and peer study benefits to support and encourage their children's participation. Students should be encouraged to engage in both methods, communicating their preferences to teachers to align activities with their requirements and enhancing academic performance and skill development. Future researchers can explore factors contributing to the effectiveness of these approaches in various educational contexts.

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